

**STRESS COUPLING ACTIVATED DAMPING:
A NEW DESIGN CONCEPT FOR IMPROVED VIBRATION DAMPING
IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES**

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ABSTRACT

Stress Coupling Activated Damping is a new design concept developed to combine the high stiffness and low weight of composite materials with significant passive damping. It uses the stress coupling effects inherent in anisotropic materials, like fiber reinforced composites, to induce large shear strains in embedded viscoelastic damping layers. By varying the ply orientation angle of the composite material along the length of components like axially-loaded struts, multiple regions of high shear are created, thus increasing the damping losses over conventional designs. Several damped cylinders and I-beams were built to test the theory and validate the modeling approach. Differences between the predicted and measured natural frequencies and loss factors for cylindrical struts in axial vibration, and for beams in bending vibration were small. Cylinders with loss factors up to 8.5% and I-beams with loss factors up to 5.7% have been built and tested. Damping in truss members for the ASTREX structure have been increased by over a factor of 10 with little change in weight and stiffness when compared to the original components.

KEYWORDS: Composite Structures, Vibration Damping

1. INTRODUCTION

The vibrational behavior of a structure is an important consideration in many design applications. Problems associated with uncontrolled vibrations include fatigue damage of the structures themselves; operator and passenger discomfort in vehicles; occupant discomfort in buildings; earthquake damage to buildings and bridges; damage to sensitive electronic equipment; antenna misalignment and blurred photographs and radar images in aircraft and satellites; and positioning errors by computer hard disk controllers. In sports equipment, excessive vibrations cause poor performance and, over long periods of time, injuries like tennis elbow.

Several methods are commonly used to reduce the effects of unwanted vibrations; these include stiffening the structure, adding rubber or viscoelastic materials to absorb vibrations (passive damping), and using electronic sensors and actuators to control vibrations (active damping).

One of the most common passive damping technologies is called Constrained Layer Damping (CLD) (1, 2). In its most common form CLD is achieved by bonding a thin layer of aluminum sheet to an existing structure with a viscoelastic adhesive. The chief limitations of CLD are that it adds weight, can only be applied to the surface of a structure, and is only effective for *out-of-plane* vibrations. CLD is most commonly used as a fix for problems on an existing structure, not as part of its original design.

Viscoelastic layers can also be embedded within a structure during lay-up (or other manufacturing process) and cocured (3). Unfortunately, the practical application of cocured damping layers has been limited by the negative effects they have on structural stiffness. In the case of a plate in bending, for example, the greatest damping is obtained when the viscoelastic layer is placed at the mid plane along the neutral axis. But since useful viscoelastic materials are very flexible, this also dramatically reduces the plate's bending stiffness. Also, note that such an embedded layer would only effectively damp out-of-plane vibrations.

In 1989, Barrett (4) attempted to broaden the application of embedded damping layers to include in-plane vibrations and to minimize the decrease in structural stiffness. His design for an axially-loaded cylindrical strut used a specific ply lay up sequence to increase damping in the part. Although this was an important step forward, the design required that complicated end fixtures be used to make it work (5,6).

2. STRESS COUPLING ACTIVATED DAMPING

A dramatic improvement over both conventional CLD and Barrett's design was developed at Brigham Young University (5, 6). This patent-applied-for concept is called Stress Coupling Activated Damping (SCAD) and promises to significantly increase the damping in composite structures without large reductions in stiffness or increases in weight. Figure 1 shows a simple part consisting of one layer of damping material embedded between two layers of fiber reinforced composite. The fiber orientation angle in the top layer (indicated by the zig-zag lines) is varied several times along the length. The fibers in the bottom layer are oriented in the opposite directions. Since all the fibers are "off-axis", an axial load will cause the upper and lower layers to move transversely in opposite directions, thus shearing the damping layer. Vibration modes which induce in-plane shear strains will cause differential axial displacements, again shearing the viscoelastic layer and increasing the damping.

It is important to understand that with Stress Coupling Activated Damping, the structure will be damped regardless of whether it experiences in-plane or out-of-plane vibrations. No matter what kind of motion is imposed, the damping layer will be sheared. Contrast this with the present technology, (e.g., CLD) in which shear strains in a damping layer are *only* produced when the part undergoes out-of-plane motion, and there is no control of in-plane vibrations. SCAD also damps out-of-plane motions more effectively than does CLD because of the additional shearing produced by the stress coupling effect.

When the part shown in Figure 1 is loaded axially, the resulting transverse motions, and thus the shear strains in the viscoelastic layer, are greatest in the locations where the fiber orientation angle changes. Therefore, if the orientation angle is varied several times along the length, as shown, areas of significant shear will be produced all along the part, not just at the ends (as is the case with Barrett's design (4)). This increases the amount of damping overall, and allows the use of simple end fixtures. For example, if the two stiffness layers are rigidly constrained by end attachments, damping is only reduced near the ends, thus having minimal effect on the bar's overall performance.

Finally, it is important to understand that the viscoelastic layer will not have much effect on the axial stiffness of the bar. The reason is that the load path remains within the fiber-reinforced composite layers without having to pass through the damping material. Therefore the stiffness is almost entirely controlled by the properties of the composite layers.

3. ANALYSIS

Analytical models of the SCAD concept have been developed for flat membranes subject to in-plane axial and shear vibrations, for thin wall cylindrical struts subject to axial and torsional vibration, and for I-beams experiencing axial and bending vibrations by Olcott, et. al. (6, 7). Since the intent of this paper is to summarize the experimental work done to prove the SCAD concept, details of the analysis will not be presented here.

Figure 1. An example of BYU's Stress Coupling Activated Damping Concept. The lines on the upper surface indicate the orientation of the fibers in the top layer. The fibers in the bottom layer are oriented in the opposite directions. When loaded in tension, as shown, the off-axis fibers produce transverse motions which intensely shear the embedded damping layer.

The models can be used to predict the effective axial modulus, E_x^* , and damping loss factor, η_x , for damped membranes and thin wall cylinders in terms of an important complex dimensionless parameter, D_o^* (with real part D_o' and imaginary part D_o''):

$$D_o^* = D_o' + iD_o'' = \frac{G_d^*}{E_{11}^*} \left(\frac{L}{t_s} \right) \left(\frac{L}{t_d} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, and where G_d^* is the complex shear modulus of the damping layer, E_{11}^* the complex modulus of the composite material in the primary (fiber) direction, L the length of each segment, t_s the thickness of each stiffness layer, and t_d the thickness of the damping layer. Other important variables are the fiber orientation angle, ϕ_o (assumed constant in each segment); the loss factor of the damping layer, η_d ; and the complex engineering constants of the stiffness layer material, E_{11}^* , E_{22}^* , E_{12}^* , and ν_{12}^* . The engineering constants for the composite layers used in the analysis were typical of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{22}^* &= 0.05E_{11}^* & E_{22}'' &= 0.01E_{22}' & E_{12}^* &= 0.05E_{11}^* & E_{12}'' &= 0.01E_{12}' \\ \nu_{12}' &= 0.28 & \nu_{12}'' &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The number of segments in the component has little effect on the results, as long as the number is greater than 6-8.

Typical analytical results are shown in Figures 3 and 4, where the loss factor, η_x , and the dimensionless axial storage modulus, $\hat{E}_x' = \text{Re}[E_x^*/E_{11}^*]$, for both flat membranes and thin wall cylindrical struts are plotted as functions of fiber orientation angle, ϕ_o , for different values of D_o' . In all the calculations, $\eta_d = 1$. (The chosen material properties for the damping and stiffness layers

gave $D'_0 \approx D''_0$.) The undamped cylinders have a loss factor of 1%, while the damped cylinders have a maximum value of 14% near $\phi_0 = 25^\circ$ and $D'_0 = 0.27$.

The analytical model predicts that a tube could be fabricated using commonly available materials with a 14% loss factor and a stiffness of only 40% that of a pure 0° cylinder. By compromising between maximum stiffness and maximum damping, a cylinder with a 10% loss factor and a stiffness equal to 70% that of a 0° tube could be constructed.

Figure 3. Loss factor, η_x , for axially-loaded thin wall tubes and flat membranes as a function of fiber angle, ϕ_0 , for values of D'_0 between 0.05 and 1.

4. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

This new damping technology was applied to two generic engineering components, cylindrical struts and I-beams, and one specific engineering structure, the ASTREX tertiary mirror support. The predicted component properties were calculated using actual material properties in the model described above. All testing was conducted using simulated free-free boundary conditions (the specimens were suspended by flexible rubber strands). The equipment used included: a piezoelectric accelerometer (PCB Piezotronics, Inc. Model 309A), a force hammer (PCB Model 086B01), signal amplifiers (PCB Model 480D06), and an HP 5423A Structural Analyzer.

4.1 Damped Thin-Wall Cylinders

Nine cylinders were fabricated, each cylinder being 51 cm (20 in) long with an inner diameter of 2.67 cm (1.05 in). Each cylinder contained two stiffness layers, each with five plies of Hercules IM7/8551-7A graphite/toughened epoxy. The damping layer thicknesses, fiber angles, and segment lengths used in each cylinder can be found in Table 1. The damping materials, listed in the table, were all film adhesives manufactured by the 3M Corporation.

The analytical model worked well, predicting the vibration frequency within 8% and damping loss factor within 15% for most cases. Some error may have arisen from the high temperature cure cycle (180°C, 4 hours) causing slight changes in the properties of the ISD-112.

Notice, none of the damped cylinders had the optimum value for D'_0 , yet one had a loss factor of 8.54%. The 0° baseline (undamped) cylinder had a loss factor of only 1.07%, which is relatively high and can be attributed to the toughened epoxy matrix resin. Other studies at BYU have

measured loss factors as low as 0.25% for non-toughened epoxies. The bending loss factors, determined by measurement only, were on the order of 20 to 30%.

Figure 4. The effective axial modulus, E_x' , for thin wall tubes and flat membranes, as a function of fiber angle, ϕ_0 , for values of D_0' between 0.05 and 1.

Table 1. Comparison of theoretical and analytical results for the natural frequencies, ω_n , and loss factors, η , for cylindrical struts in axial vibration.

Specimen Configuration						Measured Values		Predicted Values	
Label	Damping Material	Damping Layer Thickness, t_d (mm)	Fiber Angle, ϕ_0 (°)	Segment Length, L (mm)	D_0'	Natural Freq., ω_n (Hz)	Loss Factor, η (%)	Natural Freq., ω_n (Hz)	Loss Factor, η (%)
a	ISD-112	0.25	25	64	0.39	5840	6.69	5720	6.80
b	ISD-112	0.25	10	64	0.39	8390	2.30	8040	3.03
c	ISD-112	0.25	40	64	0.39	3650	6.86	3940	6.92
d	ISD-112	0.25	25	38	0.14	5690	8.54	5400	7.08
e	ISD-112	0.25	25	89	0.76	5820	5.87	5920	5.89
f	ISD-112	0.12	25	64	0.78	5830	5.97	5970	5.77
g	AF-32	0.25	25	64	24.1	5820	5.49	6470	3.06
h	None	n. a.	25	None	n. a.	6750	2.36	6560	2.02
i	None	n. a.	0	None	n. a.	8780	1.07	8780	1.00

Figure 5. Measured and predicted axial loss factors and natural frequency of damped cylindrical struts.

Figure 6. Measured and predicted axial loss factors and natural frequencies for damped tubes as a function of segment length. $L_{\text{overlap}} = 6.5$ mm (0.25 in).

4.2 Damped I-Beams

Nine I-beams were constructed with a base web and flange of $\pm 45^\circ$ cloth and an additional adhesive layer, two stiffness layers, and a damping layer in each flange as shown in Figure 9. The I-beams were approximately 780 mm (31 in) long, 76 mm (3.0 in) high, and 64 mm (2.5 in) wide. The stiffness layers with alternating fiber angles each contained six plies of Hercules IM7/8551-7A toughened graphite epoxy. The adhesive layer was 3M's AF32 and the damping layer was either 3M ISD-112 or AF32 of 0.25 or 0.13 mm (0.01 or 0.005 in) thickness. The D'_0 value for each I-beam was calculated based on the geometry and properties of only the two added stiffness layers and sandwiched viscoelastic layer. A complete modal analysis was performed for each I-beam to

isolate the first bending mode. The values of both measured and calculated loss factors and natural vibration frequencies are reported in Table 2. The damping loss factor was increased by as much as a factor of 3 and the stiffness dropped by as little as 18%. Alternatively, the stiffness could have been retained with an approximate 15% weight increase.

Figure 7. Damped I-beam, approximately 76 mm (3 in) high, 64 mm (2.5 in) wide an 780 mm (31 in) long, showing locations of added adhesive, stiffness, and damping layers. Not to scale.

Table 2. Measured and predicted natural frequencies, ω_n , and loss factors, η , for I-beams in bending vibration. The I-beams were approximately 76 mm (3 in) high, 64 mm (2.5 in) wide, and 780 mm (31 in) long.

Specimen Configuration					Measured Values		Predicted Values	
Damping Material	Damping Layer Thickness, t_d (mm)	Fiber Angle, ϕ_0 (°)	Segment Length, L (mm)	D_0'	Natural Freq., ω_n (Hz)	Loss Factor, η (%)	Natural Freq., ω_n (Hz)	Loss Factor, η (%)
ISD-112	0.25	25	51	0.21	854	5.39	898	5.16
ISD-112	0.25	10	51	0.21	1091	3.17	1119	3.52
ISD-112	0.25	40	51	0.21	683	3.80	748	5.90
ISD-112	0.25	25	76	0.47	825	5.20	910	5.24
ISD-112	0.25	25	102	0.83	848	5.68	920	5.20
ISD-112	0.12	25	51	0.41	841	4.37	919	5.35
ISD-112	0.25	25	51	47.7	913	2.59	1021	4.24
AF-32	0.25	25	51	1.28	876	3.66	966	4.24
None	n. a.	25	None	n. a.	941	1.79	1021	2.56

4.3 Damped Cylindrical Truss Members for ASTREX

The U.S. Air Force's Advanced Structural Research Experiment (ASTREX) is a 1/3 scale model of a space based laser structure (9). ASTREX is used to correlate large space structure analysis methods with actual test data, to predict and correct vibration problems on future space platforms on the ground where repairs are possible.

As part of an AFOSR sponsored research project, six damped members were constructed to replace the filament-wound members. The design objectives were to match the original members' axial stiffness and weight and increase the inherent damping loss factor as much as possible in the region of 17 Hz. This frequency corresponds to one of the first three vibration modes where a large percentage of the vibration energy is in the form of axial deformations in the tertiary mirror support members. The six new cylindrical struts were constructed with fiber angles of 24°, with

ten plies of ICI Fiberite HYE 6049W graphite/epoxy, and a single 0.25 mm (0.01 in) layer of 3M ISD-112. They had an inner diameter of 70 mm (2.75 in), and a length of 1800 mm (6 ft). This gives a D_o of approximately 0.15 at 17 Hz and 1.13 at 1.7 kHz.

The measured damping loss factor for the axial vibration mode was 6.3% at 1.7 kHz and the vibration frequency was used to determine an effective axial modulus of 67 GPa (9.6 Msi), Table 3. These correlate well with the predicted values, with the measured loss factor actually higher than predicted. The properties of the tube at 17 Hz are predicted to be 53 GPa (7.7 Msi) and 10.8%. Therefore, the ASTREX components show that large space structures can be fabricated with weight and stiffness properties equivalent to the conventional components used today, but with damping properties an order of magnitude larger than previously attainable.

Table 3. Measured and predicted natural frequencies, ω_n , and loss factors, η , for ASTREX truss elements (thin wall cylinders) in axial vibration.

Test Condition	Measured Values		Calculated Values		
	ω_n	η (%)	ω_n (Hz)	η (%)	D_o
Within ASTREX	-	-	17	10.8	0.15
Free-free	1740	6.3	1790	5.1	1.13

5. CONCLUSIONS

Stress Coupling Activated Damping is a valid design concept, applicable to a wide range of engineering problems, including plates, shells, I-beams, and cylinders. The analysis shows that for minor stiffness penalties and no weight penalties, significant increases in vibration damping properties can be achieved. Considering that many structures are not optimized, highly damped components for many structures can be designed with equivalent weights and stiffnesses and over 10 fold increases in damping. Several damped tubes were fabricated and dynamically tested to verify the damping concept and analytical models. The analytical models proved to be very accurate at predicting both stiffness and loss factor.

Information learned from the specimen testing was applied to the design and fabrication of tubes for the ASTREX structure. The new tubes match the originals in both stiffness and weight, but should have loss factors of 10.8% at the 17 Hz vibration mode in ASTREX. This loss factor is over 10 times higher than that of the original tubes. In addition, the measured loss factors for bending vibration modes between 200 and 1000 Hz were 20-30%, compared to $\leq 3\%$ for the original tubes.

6. REFERENCES

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